

Table 1. Pedigree, parentage, and agronomic characters of 8 lowland rice varieties newly released in Nigeria.

Variety	Pedigree	Parentage	Ht (cm)	Maturity (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Reaction ^a to		
						Bl	Fe toxicity	RYMV
<i>Early duration</i>								
FARO 30	FAROX 228-2-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	105	115	194	R	MR	MR
FARO 31	FAROX 228-3-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	104	118	258	R	MR	MR
FARO 32	FAROX 228-4-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	91	117	221	MR	MR	MR
FARO 33	FAROX 233-1-1-1	FARO 12/IR28	100	115	259	R	S	MR
FARO 34	FAROX 239-2-1-1	IR28/FARO 12	90	115	209	R	MR	MR
FARO 27 (check)	TOx 103	—	91	119	253	MR	MR	MR
<i>Medium duration</i>								
FARO 35	ITA 212	BG90-2 ⁴ /Tetep	97	132	210	R	S	MR
FARO 36	ITA 222	Mahsuri/IET1444	91	127	227	R	MR	MR
FARO 37	ITA 306	TOx 494-3696/ TOx 711//BG6812	105	124	203	R	MR	MR
FARO 29 (check)	BG90-2	—	97	130	216	S	MR	MR

^a S = susceptible, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

varieties were tested in zonal and multilocation trials.

All the varieties exhibit high yield potential. They are resistant to blast (Bl) and moderately resistant to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) (diseases common in the irrigated lowland ecology). In the early-duration group, FARO 30 had the highest yield (6.5 t/ha), with very good cooking quality (Table 2). FARO 34 combines long slender grains, a character highly preferred by Nigerian consumers, with very good milling and cooking qualities.

The medium-duration FARO 37 possesses high yield and long slender grains.

FARO 33 and 35 are susceptible to Fe

Table 2. Grain yields and grain qualities of 8 lowland rice varieties newly released in Nigeria.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Grain type	Cooking quality	Amylose group ^b
<i>Early duration</i>				
FARO 30	6.5	Medium bold	Very good	Intermediate
FARO 31	5.0	Medium bold	Good	Intermediate
FARO 32	5.3	Medium bold	Good	Intermediate
FARO 33	5.8	Long slender	Good	Intermediate
FARO 34	5.0	Long slender	Very good	Intermediate
FARO 27 (check)	4.9	Medium bold	Good	High
<i>Medium duration</i>				
FARO 35	5.6	Medium bold	Good	High
FARO 36	6.3	Medium bold	Good	High
FARO 37	5.8	Long slender	Good	High
FARO 29 (check)	5.6	Medium bold	Good	High

^a Av of 3 yr (1984-86) multilocation trials. ^b Intermediate = 20-25%, high = above 25%.

toxicity, the others are moderately resistant.

All early-maturing varieties have

intermediate amylose; the medium-maturing have high amylose. □

High-yielding, medium-duration variety for Tamil Nadu

S. Sevugaperumal, G. Soundrapandian, and A. Amirthadevarathnam, Agricultural Botany Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

Performance of ACM31, a promising, medium-duration culture at ACRI, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85 to 1986-87.

Variety	Mean yield ^a (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)
ACM31	6.2	92	95.6	20.6	10.4
IR20	4.7	96	101.8	22.8	13.6

^a For 3 yr.

ACM31, a high-yielding, medium-duration (132 d) variety, is a cross derivative of CO 13 and IR26. The culture is semidwarf and nonlodging with medium slender white grains. Its performance was evaluated for 3 yr 1984-85 to 1986-87 (see table). Mean grain yield was 6.2 t/ha, 31.9% more

than IR20. This variety could replace IR20 in the Periyar-Vaigai River ayacut area. □

Promising, long-duration rice variety for Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu

T. Sundaram, O.R. Pillai, S. Sevugaperumal, J. G. Robinson, and A. S. Mathar, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Thirupathisaram 629901, Tamil Nadu, India

Traditional rice varieties are grown in about 40% (9,200 ha) of the rice area in